

Providing access to cost-efficient, replicable,
safe and flexible CCUS

Capture Ready Waste to Energy Plants

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About ACCSESS

If CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) is to become a relevant, large-scale technology for cutting carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, several barriers need to be addressed, and its deployment must be accelerated.

ACCSESS works to address key challenges to the successful implementation of CCS across Europe: namely, challenges related to CO₂ capture, CCS chains, and societal acceptance. The project focuses on four industrial sectors with the potential to drastically reduce CO₂ emissions by implementing CCS: waste-to-energy, pulp and paper, cement, and biorefineries.

ACCSESS started in May 2021. Its consortium consists of 18 partners from eight different European countries.

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Abstract
<p>The revised BREF WI (Best Available Technologies REference document for Waste Incineration), entered into force in December 2023. It does not address CCS but may very well affect its possible implementation. To ensure a smooth implementation of CCS, it is crucial to ensure that BREF compliance anticipates (or at least considers) CCS requirements and needs.</p> <p>This deliverable presents and discusses BAT-AELs with a perspective on possible impact on downstream solvent-based CO₂ capture process. Combining extensive data on WtE flue gas composition and dynamics together with available literature on CCS tests at WtE plants, this deliverable presents techno-economic analysis of the impact of interface between the APC and the solvent-based CO₂ capture process. Furthermore, the deliverable provides recommendations and considerations when integrating a post-combustion CO₂ capture process in capture-ready WtE plant.</p>

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Document Purpose

The revised BREF WI (Best Available Technologies REference document for Waste Incineration) was published in December 2019 and does not address CO₂ capture. However, the revised BREF WI may very well affect the implementation of CO₂ capture in Waste to Energy (WtE) plants. In addition to being legally binding (which was not the case for the previous BREF), it will lead to stricter emission limits for critical pollutants and require the monitoring of additional chemical species (e.g. NH₃) and new sampling methods. The respective national authorities have four years (from BREF publication) to ensure that all WtE plants comply with the new regulation. This compliance may require only minor adjustments but might also mean significant retrofitting of various plant components, especially in the APC system. To ensure a smooth implementation of CO₂ capture in WtE plants, it is crucial to ensure that any BREF compliance modification/retrofitting anticipates CCS requirements and needs and even promotes synergies. The document establishes a set of guidelines for future Capture-ready WtE plants.

1.2 List of Acronyms and abbreviations

AMP/PZ - 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP)/ piperazine (PZ) mixture
APC/FGT – Air Pollution Control / Flue Gas Treatment
BAT - Best Available Technology
BAT-AELs BAT Associated Emission Levels
BF – Bag Filter
BREF WI - Best Available Technologies REference document for Waste Incineration
CCUS – Carbon Capture Use and Storage
CEWEP – The Confederation of European WtE Plants
CHP – Combined Heat and Power
DCC – Direct Contact Cooler
DSI - Dry Sorbent Injection
ESP – ElectroStatic Precipitator
FGT/APC – Flue Gas Treatment /Air Pollution Control
IEAGHG - IEA Greenhouse Gas R& D Programme
MEA - monoethanolamine
MSW – Municipal Solid Waste
SCR – Selective Catalytic Reduction (for NO_x)
SNCR – Selective Non Catalytic Reduction (for NO_x)
SWS – semi wet scrubber
WS – Wet scrubber
WtE – Waste-to-Energy

1.3 Relation to other deliverables

No relation to other public ACCESS deliverables.

2 WtE PLANT WITH CO₂ CAPTURE - OVERVIEW

This section provides an overview of the different components of a WtE plant with CO₂ capture and a short description of its implications. The CO₂ capture technology considered in this work is post-combustion capture by reactive absorption using solvents. The main components of a WtE plant with CO₂ capture are the incinerator with energy recovery and flue gas cleaning (combined, referred to as the WtE plant) and a downstream CO₂ capture plant.

2.1 WtE plant

Fuel Reception and Storage	Combustion and Boiler	Flue Gas Treatment	Energy Recovery	Residue Handling and Treatment
1 Tipping hall	4 Feed hopper	14 Electrostatic precipitator	23 Extraction-condensation turbine	29 Bottom ash extractor
2 Shredder	5 Ram feeder	15 Sodium bicarbonate injection	24 Air cooled condenser	30 Bottom ash bunker
3 Solid fuel bunker	6 Hitachi Zosen Inova grate	16 Fabric filter 1	25 District heating heat exchanger	31 Bottom ash crane
4 Solid fuel crane	7 Four-pass steam boiler	17 SCR DeNOx	26 Process steam extraction	
	8 External Economiser	18 Heat exchanger 1	27 Trafo	
	9 Secondary air injection	19 Fabric filter 2	28 Electricity Export	
	10 Secondary air fan	20 Induced draft fan		
	11 Recirculated flue gas injection	21 Heat exchanger 2		
	12 Recirculated flue gas fan	22 Stack		
	13 Primary air fan			

Figure 1: A typical WtE plant.¹

The key elements of a typical European WtE plant can be briefly described as such:

- The bulky waste is tipped into a bunker with a few days' worth of operation.
- Cranes (either manually or automatically operated) deposit waste into a shaft leading to the feeding system. Cranes also mix the waste stored in the bunker to mitigate heterogeneity.
- The different steps of combustion (drying, devolatilisation, oxidation) take place along a moving grate with both under and over-fire air added, which is taken from the shaft bunker's ambient air. (Alternative technologies include rotary kilns and fluidised beds).
- The hot exhaust gas reaches heat-exchange surfaces to produce steam or hot water. The heat-exchanger setup is adapted to the energy produced (hot water, steam, processed heat, district heat, power, heat & power). Corrosion, slagging, and fouling are common ash-related challenges.
- The gas is then cleaned through an advanced air pollution control (APC)/ flue gas treatment (FGT) system. Three main classes exist: dry, semi-dry/semi-wet, and wet systems (see details in the next section), depending on the amount of water involved. The main

¹ <https://www.hz-inova.com/projects/lucerne-che/>

components are electrostatic precipitator (ESP)/filtering (to remove dust and particles), scrubber/lime (for DeSO_x, removal of acid gases), SCR/SNCR (for DeNO_x), and active carbon (mainly for dioxins/furans and Hg).

2.2 Air pollution control (APC)/Flue gas treatment (FGT) systems

Air pollution control systems play a crucial role in minimising the environmental impact of waste-to-energy (WtE) plants. These systems are designed to remove pollutants and particulate matter from the flue gases generated during combustion, ensuring compliance with stringent emission regulations.

Modern APC systems comprise multiple stages for removing fly ashes, inorganic and organic gases, heavy metals, and dioxins from the flue gas (see Figure 2). BREF WI [1] gives an overview of the main steps and technologies for the main types of FGT/APC systems found in WtE plants across Europe, representing over 400 possible combinations.

Figure 2: Stages of APC system in WtE plants

Dust removal

The first APC measure downstream of the energy recovery section is the removal of dust/fly ash. Dust removal can be accomplished by cyclones, ESPs, fabric, baghouse filters, and venturi scrubbers.

Acid gas abatement

Acid gases such as HCl and SO₂ are present in waste incineration flue gas that must be removed. This is an essential step of the APC system. Dry, semi-wet or wet scrubbers are used for acid gas abatement.

In dry sorbent injection (DSI), the adsorption agent is fed into the flue gas as dry powder. The reaction products are solid and must be removed, usually using a bag filter. Overdosing of the agent leads to an increase in the amount of residues if no recirculation of the unreacted agent is carried out. Hydrated lime and sodium bicarbonate are standard alkaline adsorption agents for DSI. Sodium bicarbonate is effective over a temperature range of 120-300 °C. However, reaction kinetics improve with higher temperatures. According to BREF WI [1], typical sodium bicarbonate consumption is 6-12 kg/tonne of waste for MSW. Thus, higher dosing might increase the acid gas removal and might be a solution if the CCS plant requires less acid gases than what is presently emitted from an MSW plant.

In the semi-wet scrubber (SWS) process, water and hydrated lime are injected separately or as a suspension. The heat of the flue gas evaporates the water, and the reaction products are solids that must be removed as dust, e.g., in a bag filter. SWS processes are typically more efficient than dry processes and require less overdosing of the absorption agent.

Wet scrubbers are used for acid gas removal in wet flue gas treatment processes. The flue gas is cooled to 50 – 70 °C and flows through a scrubbing liquid, such as water or an alkaline solution. The acid gases dissolve in the scrubbing liquid and are neutralised. Depending on their solubilities, the resulting products remain dissolved in the scrubbing liquid, e.g., as calcium chloride, or precipitate, e.g., as calcium sulphate.

Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x) abatement

The formation of NO_x in waste incineration originates from nitrogen compounds present in the waste. Two main approaches to NO_x abatement are Selective Non-Catalytic Reduction (SNCR) and Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR).

The SNCR process involves injecting ammonia or urea into the high-temperature flue gas stream. The SNCR process relies on maintaining the optimal temperature range (typically between 850°C and 1100°C) for the reduction reactions to occur efficiently. This temperature window is critical. The injected reagent reacts with the NO_x in the presence of oxygen, converting it into nitrogen and water vapour. SNCR systems are generally less expensive and easier to install than SCR systems, making them a popular choice for smaller WtE plants or as a complementary system to SCR. However, SNCR systems typically have lower NO_x removal efficiencies, ranging from 30% to 75%, depending on the operating conditions and reagent injection strategy.

Selective Catalytic Reduction (SCR) is a highly effective technology for reducing nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions in waste-to-energy (WtE) plants. In this process, a catalyst facilitates the conversion of NO_x into nitrogen and water vapour. The SCR system typically involves injecting ammonia or urea into the flue gas stream, which then reacts with the NO_x in the presence of the catalyst. The catalyst, often made of vanadium, titanium, or zeolite-based materials, provides a surface for the reduction reaction to occur efficiently. SCR systems are typically installed downstream of the combustion process, where the flue gas temperature is within the optimal range for the catalyst to function effectively (typically between 300°C and 400°C). SCR systems can achieve NO_x removal efficiencies of up to 95%, making them a highly effective solution for meeting stringent emission regulations in WtE plants.

Dioxin and heavy metals removal:

Dioxins (and furans) are formed in the incineration process. The formation mechanisms of these compounds are complex. Activated carbon adsorbs and removes dioxins and furans from the flue gas. Another approach is catalytic oxidation, which destroys dioxins and furans through oxidation reactions.

Heavy metals in the flue gas can be removed by activated carbon, which adsorbs heavy metals like mercury, or by dry or wet scrubbers, which remove heavy metals through chemical reactions.

2.3 CO₂ capture plant

Figure 3 below shows a simple process diagram of a typical solvent-based post-combustion capture process. It is a cyclical process in which the solvent is contacted countercurrent to gas flow in an absorber to capture the CO₂. This solvent is then sent to the stripper to regenerate it and release the CO₂. The regenerated solvent is sent back to the absorber to capture CO₂, while the CO₂ is sent to a purification and compression section for transport and storage.

Figure 3: Process flow diagram of a typical solvent-based post-combustion capture process.

Solvent regeneration in the stripper requires heat and is the main source of energy consumption in the capture process. Thus, the solvent process will require steam and will typically be integrated with the steam cycle of the WtE plant. The energy required for solvent regeneration depends on the solvent used. Other sources of energy consumption are the blower/fan to move the exhaust gas through the absorber, overcoming its pressure drop, and pumps to circulate the solvent.

One of the challenges of solvent-based post-combustion capture is solvent degradation and environmental emissions. This also depends on the solvent used in the process. Amine-based solvents with ethanol amine have been studied the most concerning solvent degradation and related emissions. The primary sources of solvent degradation are heat, O₂, CO₂ and impurities in the exhaust gas, such as SO_x and NO_x. These two impurities are most studied as they are commonly present in combustion exhaust gases. Oxidation degradation is the most prominent source of degradation, followed by thermal degradation. Solvents such as potassium carbonate do not inherently have issues with degradation and emissions. However, additives/activators added to the solvent, such as enzymes, could be impacted by impurities in the flue gas.

2.4 Challenges of integrating CO₂ capture in a WtE plant

Integration of solvent-based CO₂ capture in a WtE plant will most certainly require modifications/retrofits to the WtE plant. Some of the main challenges of integrating CO₂ capture in a WtE plant are:

- **Additional emissions:** Solvent-based CO₂ capture plants can result in further emissions from the plant. These include solvent degradation products, aerosols, and other volatile compounds that can be emitted from the absorber and desorber units. The extent of these emissions depends on factors like the solvent type, operating conditions, and plant design. Proper solvent management and emission control strategies are crucial to minimise these additional emissions and their potential environmental impact.

- **Flue gas cleaning:** Most CO₂ capture solvents are affected by flue gas composition and impurities present, particularly SO_x, NO_x, and heavy metals. Thus, adding a CO₂ capture plant downstream of the WtE plant will impose requirements on flue gas composition from the APC. This will depend on solvent type, etc, and could be more stringent than those set out by BAT WI. This is a critical aspect of the integration and will be the main focus of this document.
- **Energy integration:** Maintaining stable operation and energy delivery is critical for WtE plants as they produce heat for district heating and/or electricity. When integrating with a CO₂ capture facility that uses thermal energy for solvent regeneration, appropriate design and integration with energy recovery are critical to maintaining suitable heat and/or electricity production levels. This is a key challenge identified by WtE operators. The relative importance of exporting heat compared to electricity, the steam parameters in the facility, and the CO₂ capture technology (in terms of the quality and quantity of heat required for solvent regeneration) will affect the type of integration.
- **Space:** Integrating a CO₂ capture plant will require space for installing the capture plant's process units and the CO₂ processing unit for transporting CO₂. WtE plants are typically installed in urban settings, limiting the availability of land for the additional units for CO₂ capture and processing.

2.5 Status on WtE plants and CO₂ capture

Table 1 below shows an overview of the many WtE CCUS projects launched across Europe in recent years. CEWEP presented it on February 6th, 2024; a similar list was given in their GHGT conference paper.²

Table 1: WtE CCUS projects across Europe (Ref. CEWEP)

Belgium	Indaver Power-to-Methanol project (Antwerp@c, Port of Antwerp)
Denmark	CCS projects (ARC, Copenhagen), (Vestforbrænding, Glostrup), (ARGO, Roskilde) as part of the C4 - Carbon Capture Cluster Copenhagen
Finland	CCU Carbon2x pilot (Fortum, Riihimäki); EnergySampo CCU project (Westenergy, Mustasaari) + other CCU Power-to-Gas projects
France	CCU pilot project for CO ₂ use in algae production in the Paris area (SUEZ, Créteil), (Syctom, Saint-Ouen)
Germany	CCU projects for the production of synthetic methanol (EEW, Helmstedt); (ZASt, Zella-Mehlis)
Italy	Ravenna Hub CCS project (Herambiente, Ravenna); Hot Potassium Carbonate Test Installation (A2A, Cortelona)
Netherlands	Various CCUS projects (Twence, Hengelo), (AVR, Duiven), (AVR, Rozenburg), (AEB, Amsterdam), (HVC, Alkmaar); HyNetherlands CCU project for methanol production (EEW, Delfzijl); OSIRIS project for CO ₂ supply to two greenhouse clusters (PreZero, Roosendaal), etc.
Norway	CCS Longship Project (Hafslund Oslo Celsio, Klemetsrud); CCS Borg CO ₂ cluster (Frevar, Fredrikstad), (Kvitebjørn Bio-El, Fredrikstad), (Sarpsborg Avfallsenergi, Sarpsborg); other projects (Statkraft Varme, Trondheim), (Returkraft, Kristiansand), (BIR Ressurs, Bergen), etc.
Portugal	Power-to-Liquid project for the production of synthetic aviation fuels (LIPOR, Porto)
Sweden	HySkies CCU project for synthetic aviation fuels production (Vattenfall, Uppsala); CCS studies (Renova, Gothenburg), (SYSAV; Malmö);
Switzerland	CCS investigation study (KVA Linth, Niederurnen); All 29 Swiss WtE plants committed to CCS on the long-term
UK	CCS East Coast Cluster (SUEZ, Haverton Hill/Teesside); CCS Hynet North West project (Viridor, Runcorn), etc.

...and many more on-going feasibility studies, pilots projects, etc.

² Poretti, Fabio and Stengler, Ella, The Climate Roadmap of the European Waste-to-Energy Sector | The path to Carbon Negative (November 23, 2022). Proceedings of the 16th Greenhouse Gas Control Technologies Conference (GHGT-16) 23-24 Oct 20224

3 EMISSION LEVELS IN WTE FLUE GASES

Several integration aspects must be considered when implementing solvent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture to WtE plants. One of them is the flue gas composition and the possible adverse effect of some compounds on the solvent. It is, therefore, essential to know the emission levels of the different flue gas compounds after cleaning before the CO₂ capture process. The present chapter provides an overview of the authority regulations regarding emissions limits, the reported emission data from existing WtE plants, and the variations in emissions concentrations that can likely appear in the flue gas of WtE plants. In Ch. 4, this will be compared with existing recommendations for solvents to evaluate if additional measures need to be taken in the flue gas cleaning before the CO₂ capture plant.

3.1 BAT-associated emission levels

The easiest solution for a capture-ready WtE plant concerning flue gas composition would be if the authority-regulated emissions limits would be sufficient for the capture plant and the solvent to be used. The EU Best Available Techniques (BAT) Reference Document for Waste Incineration [1], abbreviated BREF WI, from 2019 provides updated values for BAT-associated emission levels (BAT-AELs). The emission limits from the revised BREF WI became legally binding in December 2023, and all plants should follow these requirements.

The emission limits are summarised in Table 3-1. They are given as intervals, so the national and regional authorities have some flexibility to set different values according to specific conditions, such as the type of air pollution control (APC) system and waste quality.

Table 3-1: BAT-associated emission levels (BAT-AELs) from BREF WI from 2019.

Flue gas compounds	Unit	BAT-AELs		Monitoring frequency ⁽⁵⁾	Averaging period ^{(6), (7)}
		New plant	Existing plant		
SO ₂	mg/Nm ³	5 – 30	5 – 40	Continuous	Daily
HCl ⁽¹⁾	mg/Nm ³	< 2 – 6	< 2 – 8	Continuous	Daily
HF	mg/Nm ³	< 1		Continuous	Daily or sampling period
NO _x	mg/Nm ³	50 – 120 ⁽²⁾	50 – 150 ^{(2), (3)}	Continuous	Daily
NH ₃	mg/Nm ³	2 – 10 ⁽²⁾	2 – 10 ^{(2), (4)}	Continuous	Daily
CO	mg/Nm ³	10 – 50		Continuous	Daily
Dust	mg/Nm ³	< 2 – 5		Continuous	Daily
Cd+Tl	mg/Nm ³	0.005 – 0.02		Every 6 month	Sampling period
Sb+As+Pb+Cr+Co +Cu+Mn+Ni+V	mg/Nm ³	0.01 – 0.3		Every 6 month	Sampling period
TVOC	mg/Nm ³	< 3 – 10		Continuous	Daily
PCDD/F	ng I-TEQ/Nm ³	< 0.01 – 0.04	< 0.01 – 0.06	Every 6 month	Sampling period
PCDD/F + dioxin-like PCBs	ng WHO-TEQ/Nm ³	< 0.01 – 0.06	< 0.01 – 0.08	Every 6 month	Sampling period
Hg	µg/Nm ³	< 5 – 20		Continuous	Daily or sampling period

Comments to table values:

- 1) Using a wet scrubber can achieve the lower end of the BAT-AEL range; the higher end may be associated with dry sorbent injection.
- 2) The lower end of the BAT-AEL range can be achieved when using SCR.
- 3) The higher end of the BAT-AEL range is 180 mg/Nm³, where SCR is not applicable.

- 4) For existing plants fitted with SNCR without wet abatement techniques, the higher end of the BAT-AEL range is 15 mg/Nm³.
- 5) Continuous measurements are measurements using an automated measuring system permanently installed on site.
- 6) The daily average is averaged over one day based on valid half-hourly averages.
- 7) Averages over the sampling period are the average of three consecutive measurements of at least 30 minutes each.

The emission levels are expressed as mass per volume of dry flue gas at normal conditions, temperature 0 °C, 1 atmosphere pressure (273 K and 101.3 kPa), and a reference oxygen concentration of 11 vol-% dry. The emission values will often be needed as volumetric ppm values. These values are calculated and shown in Appendix A.

As described in the comments to Table 3-1, reported emission values shall be based on 30-minute averages. Any incidents or irregular situations that might cause short periods with much higher emission levels will be less visible from these reported values. If knowledge about possible higher short-term peaks is essential to the CO₂ capture process, the more frequently logged raw data from the plant must be considered.

3.2 Emission levels for reference lines in BREF WI

The 2016 data collection from the BREF WI includes emission data for 355 emissions monitoring points from WtE reference lines and plants used in the work with the BREF WI. This comprehensive data set provides emission data from existing plants that can be compared with emission limits and requirements given by the CO₂ capture plant.

For each continuously measured emission component, half-hourly average concentrations for 2014 were collected. Appendix C details the nine flue gas components: SO₂, HCl, HF, NO_x, NH₃, CO, dust, TVOC, and Hg. The vertical lines in each figure give the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

From the figures, HCl and NO_x are components for which rather many lines have problems meeting based on daily averages. However, these emission values should be used with a high level of care when making conclusions regarding the readiness level of the European WtE plant for CO₂ capture. The data are ten years old, there are known inaccuracies in the data [1], and the size and age of the plants are unknown from the BREF report.

3.3 Emission levels and emission variations for ACCESS WtE lines

The former section provided a large amount of emissions data from the BREF WI work, using mainly half-hourly averages. The ACCESS project has also gathered emissions data from several WtE lines related to the project. This data collection contains series with higher time resolution than data averaged according to regulations. This data set was collected to do a more detailed evaluation of emissions concentrations and their potential variation in a shorter time frame than what will be visible from reported averages. WtE is subject to unstable, fluctuating conditions and shorter periods with high emissions, referred to as "incidents". They can significantly impact any downstream process, including carbon capture. It is worthwhile to note that the incidents can have multiple possible causes. They are often associated with the waste properties, especially its composition and heterogeneity.

The analysis was carried out for the following species: NO_x, SO₂, CO, dust, HCl, and NH₃. The data set also includes CO₂, O₂, and H₂O concentrations. O₂ is especially important with respect to solvent degradation. The analysis covers 4-12 months of operation and is meant to be representative of the plants' typical behaviour.

Appendix D presents the results in detail for each species. The figures show statistical parameters to describe emissions for the WtE lines during normal, relatively stable operation, i.e., typical behaviour. The figures include the average value and the standard deviation for the studied period, the maximum value observed in the period, and the percentage of measured points above the lower BAT-AEL bound. It should be noted that the average is for the whole period, not daily averages, as is the basis for regulatory emissions reporting.

Appendix D also includes tables for each species, giving a quantitative/qualitative analysis of the significant fluctuations in emissions, the so-called “incidents”, found in the data sets. The tables show the peak value observed, how fast the increase/decrease is, the typical duration of such an incident, and how often such an incident happens in a given WtE line. If the typical plant behaviour shows regular incidents/fluctuations with high emission values for some time, it is essential that the CO₂ capture process is designed to cope with this.

The sub-sections below present a summary of the findings for each of the analysed species. For more details, refer to Appendix D.

3.3.1 NO_x emissions

NO_x emissions from ten different WtE lines were analysed. The average values are all within the new BAT-AEL values (note again that the average values are here averaged over the whole period, not daily averages as are the basis for BAT-AELs). SCR technologies can meet the low-end BAT-AEL values. SNCR technologies show slightly higher average values but are still well below the maximum BAT-AEL limits. SNCR combined with dry desulphurisation shows the highest value. These ten lines perform better than most of the lines included in the BREF WI study.

Maximum NO_x values for these ten lines are about 200 – 450 mg/Nm³. Incidents with emissions above the maximum BAT-AEL limit can last about 1 – 5 hours. The frequency of such incidents seems to be weekly or bi-weekly for the studied lines.

3.3.2 SO₂ emissions

Nine different WtE lines' SO₂ emissions during normal operation were analysed. Most of the lines are below the lower BAT-AEL limit for SO₂, and all of them are well below the upper limit values for both existing and new plants. The data are not conclusive on whether dry or wet desulphurisation gives the best values.

Maximum values are 100 mg/Nm³ and up to 400 mg/Nm³, i.e., ten times the upper BAT-AEL limit. The duration and frequency of incidents with elevated emission levels are lower than for NO_x. Duration is typically 1 – 2 hours, and occurrences are generally bi-weekly or more seldom.

3.3.3 CO emissions

CO emissions were analysed for seven different WtE lines. Average values are generally well below the maximum BAT-AEL limit (but note again; the averages are for the whole period and

distinct from the daily averaging that must be done for reporting. However, they can provide a rough comparison).

The incidents in the data show scattered results for peak values, duration, and frequency. The highest peak value was found to be 365 mg/Nm³. Incidents with emission levels above BAT-AEL occur weekly but generally with a short duration of about 10 minutes.

3.3.4 Dust emissions

Dust emissions from seven different WtE lines show relatively low values, below the lower end of the BAT-AEL. Incidents with somewhat higher values generally last 2 – 4 hours. They occur only monthly or more rarely, except for two lines where slightly higher dust emissions are regular and connected to regular filter cleaning/flushing.

3.3.5 HCl emissions

HCl emissions for six different WtE lines show low average values, well below the lower-end BAT-AEL value of 2 mg/Nm³. The highest peak values are 47 and 48 mg/Nm³. Periods with elevated HCl emissions, i.e., above the maximum BAT-AEL of 8 mg/Nm³, occur only monthly and with 4 and 7 hours duration based on the data from these six lines.

3.3.6 NH₃ emissions

Six different WtE lines were analysed for NH₃ emissions. Very low average values are reported for four of them. One line is just at the upper BAT-AEL limit of 10 mg/Nm³, and one line is above with 15 mg/Nm³. This line is the only SNCR line. It also has the highest standard deviation and by far the highest maximum value in the data set.

3.3.7 Flue gas O₂ concentrations

The oxygen concentration of the flue gas is important with respect to oxidative solvent degradation. The data from more than ten WtE lines analysed in this study show average O₂ concentrations ranging from about 5 vol-% dry to about 11 vol-% dry.

4 IMPURITY TOLERANCES FOR CO₂ CAPTURE

The tolerance of the CO₂ capture solvent to various components in the flue gas from the WtE plant will determine if additional units or modified operation of the existing components in the APC system will be required. In the literature, clear recommendations on concentration limits in the flue gas entering the CO₂ capture process are scarce. In an IEAGHG technical report on CCS from WtE, the following concentration limits were recommended to keep the solvent degradation at acceptable levels [2]:

- Maximum SO₂ concentration: 10 ppm
- Maximum NO_x (as NO₂) concentration: 20 ppm
- Maximum total dust concentration: 10 ppm
- Maximum HCl concentration: 10 ppm

No clear definition of what is regarded as acceptable solvent degradation is provided. For some components, these limits are stricter than the legally binding BAT-AELs in **Error! Reference source not found.** For new and existing plants, the maximum allowable SO₂ emission level (10.5 and 14 ppm) exceeds the maximum concentration of 10 ppm as described above. For NO_x, even the lowest emission level (24.4 ppm) exceeds the requirement of 20 ppm. Therefore, if the IEAGHG recommendations are followed strictly, modifications of the APC system to reduce SO₂ emissions for some plants and NO_x emissions for most plants will be necessary.

As shown in Section 3.3, the emission levels from a WtE plant will vary over time and can be significantly higher than the reported average values during incidents/fluctuations. In practice, continuously keeping the concentrations below strict limits is not achievable, and, likely, the CO₂ capture plant will occasionally be exposed to higher concentrations. Based on practical experience from the operation of pilot plants, there is a trade-off between allowing a certain amount of solvent degradation and the additional capital/operating costs associated with extensive flue gas treatment.

This section relies on openly available reports and scientific papers describing pilot plant testing of solvent-based CO₂ capture in environments relevant to WtE. The goal is to understand the effect of flue gas cleaning on solvent degradation and solvent-related emissions from the capture plant, to make recommendations for capture-ready CO₂ capture from WtE plants.

Section 4.1 gives an overview of relevant pilot plant campaigns documented in the literature. Table 4-1 shows the flue gas composition at the absorber inlet and which upstream flue gas treatment steps and treatment/handling steps are included in the different CO₂ capture plants.

4.1 Summary of relevant pilot plant campaigns

Table 4-1: Concentration of main flue gas components and summary of gas treatment and solvent handling measures from relevant pilot campaigns [3], [4], [5], [6].

Plant	Flue gas source	Solvent	O2 conc. (vol%)		CO2 conc. (vol%)		SOx conc.		NOx conc.		Flue gas treatment before absorber				Treatment/handling within capture plant		
			wet	dry	wet	dry	ppm	mg/Nm3	ppm	mg/Nm3	SOx removal	NOx removal	Particle removal	Other treatment	DCC/pre-scrubber	Reclaiming	Solvent filter
Niederaussem	Coal (lignite)	MEA and AMP/PZ			5	14.2	<1		120-200	Wet limestone	SCR	Wet ESP can be used if necessary	Spray scrubber with water for aerosol removal was tested. Dosing with thiosulfate for additional NO2 removal was also tested.	DCC dosed with NaOH for extra SO2 removal	Solvent ion exchange was tested	Active carbon filter could be used if needed	Water wash, dry bed, acid wash
Esbjerg	Coal	MEA, CASTOR 1 and CASTOR 2			5-9	12	<10		<65	Wet limestone	High dust SCR	Cold-sided ESP		No, flue gas from power plant sent directly to absorber	Reclaimer dosed with soda	Carbon filtering of rich MEA	
Technology Centre Mongstad Combined Heat and Power	Natural gas	MEA 30 wt%, Aker Solutions S21, S26, CESAR 1			14.8	3.7	<1		<6					DCC with water only			Water wash
TCM RFCC	Catalytic cracker	CESAR 1, multiple others			4.3	13.2	27-70		50-118					DCC with water only			Water wash
Loy Yang	Coal	MEA 30 wt%	4-5		10-11			120-200	150-250	No	No	ESP	Knock-out drum before DCC	DCC operated as caustic wash			Water wash
CAER 0.1 MWth	Coal	MEA 30 wt%, CAER-B2	6		14			170-250	80-90	Wet FGD		High-temp cyclone	Knock-out drum One scrubber before SOx removal for HCl, mercury and others. A condensing scrubber after de-SOx for turning water into droplets. Filter for HCl/HF removal before capture plant	No, but has knock-out drum	Yes		
Amager Bakke	Municipal solid waste	MEA 30 wt%			7.25			12.3	1.5	20.2	Scrubber using lime	SCR	Electric filter for fly ash		No, but has knock-out drum	Carbon filter for making solvent clearer and stabilizing iron content.	Water wash, dry bed, acid wash (0.1 M sulphuric acid), water polish section
Fortum Oslo Varme	Municipal solid waste	Shell DC-103 (amine)			7.3			11.3	7	45.1	K1, K2: Dry Ca(OH)2 + activated carbon K3: 4-stage wet scrubber	K1, K2: SNCR K3: SCR	K1, K2: Series of bag filters K3: ESP	Yes, pure DCC	No	Activated carbon filter can be brought online when required	No
AVR Duiven	Municipal solid waste	MEA 30 wt%	5-10					10	3.3	67.8				Yes, most likely pure DCC	"Bleed and feed" strategy		Water wash, acid wash

Figure 4-1 shows the typical SO_x concentration in the flue gas entering the absorber column for the different pilot plants. The concentrations vary significantly between plants, covering a range between 0.35 and 210 ppm. The coal-fired plants with wet de-SO_x units (Niederaussem and Esbjerg) and the three WtE plants have the lowest SO_x concentrations. Three pilot plants are treating flue gas with much higher concentrations than the IEAGHG limit of 10 ppm.

Figure 4-1: Typical flue gas SO_x concentrations at the absorber column inlet of selected pilot plants for solvent-based CO₂ capture. The figure on the right focuses on the low-concentration range.

Significant variations are also observed for the NO_x concentration of the flue gas at the CO₂ capture plant inlet. The concentrations for the different pilot campaigns are shown in Figure 4-2. Apart from the natural gas-fired CHP plant at TCM, the WtE plants have the lowest NO_x concentrations. The lowest concentration is seen for Amager Bakke, which has a selective catalytic reduction system for NO_x removal. The Klemetsrud WtE plant (Fortum Oslo Varme) mixes flue gas from three lines with different de-NO_x technologies and, therefore, has a slightly higher inlet concentration. For most pilot plants, the NO_x concentrations exceed the maximum limit of 20 ppm recommended by IEAGHG.

Figure 4-2: Typical flue gas NO_x concentrations at the absorber column inlet of selected pilot plants for solvent-based CO₂ capture. The figure on the right focuses on the low-concentration range.

For a few of the pilot campaigns in the literature, the rate of solvent degradation is reported in addition to the flue gas composition. This information is available for testing of MEA [7] and AMP/PZ [8] at Niederaussem, MEA at Esbjerg [9], MEA at Technology Centre Mongstad and MEA at the AVR Duiven WtE plant [5]. Although the amount of data is limited, the results from these studies can be used to indicate the relationship between SO_x and NO_x concentration and solvent degradation. In Figure 4-3, the solvent degradation rate vs. the SO_x and NO_x concentration in the flue gas is shown.

Figure 4-3: Solvent degradation rate vs. SO_x and NO_x concentration in the flue gas entering the absorber column. The green marker indicates a result from the AVR Duiven WtE plant, and the blue marker indicates a result from testing with AMP/PZ. Orange markers indicate campaigns with MEA from non-WtE flue gases.

As the figure shows, the degradation rate seems to increase with increasing SO_x content in the flue gas. High NO_x concentrations do not give higher degradation rates. The lowest degradation rates are achieved at the Niederaussem plant, which has the highest NO_x concentration of the pilot plants in question but a very low flue gas SO_x concentration. However, it is difficult to isolate the effect of a single species based on these graphs due to possible intertwined effects that can add up or cancel out one another.

The oxygen content in the flue gas will also influence the solvent degradation rate. Figure 4-4 shows the relationship between flue gas O₂ concentration and solvent degradation. Increased oxygen content leads to increased solvent losses, which is expected since oxidative degradation is a significant degradation pathway for amine solvents [3].

Figure 4-4: Solvent degradation rate vs. O₂ concentration in the flue gas entering the absorber column. The blue marker indicates a campaign with AMP/PZ. Orange markers indicate campaigns with MEA.

Since the amount of data on solvent degradation rates is limited, Figure 4-3 and Figure 4-4 alone should not be used to conclude the required level of flue gas treatment to make a WtE plant capture-ready. Furthermore, other contaminants than SO_x and NO_x are likely to affect the stability

of the solvent. In Sections 4.2 and 4.3, more details from pilot campaigns using the AMP/PZ solvent and testing on flue gas from WtE plants are given, to understand more about the effect of various gas components and their concentrations in these specific cases.

4.2 Campaigns using AMP/PZ

The most important test campaign for the AMP/PZ solvent is the long-term test at the Niederaussem coal-fired power plant in Germany ([8], [10]). The pilot plant was operated for over 40 months, and it was continuously operating without replacement of the solvent inventory, although fresh solvent was added eight times during the test. A key finding from the testing was that the AMP/PZ solvent demonstrates slow-progressing linear degradation behaviour, which differs from the exponential degradation observed for MEA towards the end of the solvent lifetime. Table 4-2 shows the typical flue gas composition observed during the test. Due to the NaOH-dosed DCC, the SO₂ concentration at the absorber inlet is very low. Since low degradation rates were observed in this campaign, a dust concentration of <2 mg/m³ before the DCC seems acceptable to avoid problems for the solvent.

Table 4-2: Typical flue gas composition observed during AMP/PZ test at Niederaussem.

Component	Unit	Value
CO ₂ content at absorber inlet	vol% (dry)	15.2
O ₂ content after de-SO _x	vol% (dry)	5.5
SO ₂ content at absorber inlet	mg/m ³ (dry, STP)	<1
Dust content before DCC	mg/m ³ (dry, STP)	<2
NO _x content at absorber inlet	mg/m ³ (dry, STP)	100-180
NO ₂ content at absorber inlet	mg/m ³ (dry)	1-4

Several solvent management and additional flue gas-cleaning strategies were investigated during the campaign. Below are summarised the effect of these measures on solvent degradation and general conclusions from the work.

- Based on the long-term test campaign results, **no unequivocal concentration limit** that must be followed to keep solvent degradation at acceptable levels can be specified for individual contaminants or the sum of different contaminants.
- Additional pre-treatment reduced the flue gas NO₂ concentration by around 80% (from around 4 to around 0.8 mg/m³) but did not affect reducing solvent degradation or the concentration of nitrosamines (a main degradation product for the AMP/PZ solvent).
- Removal of anionic compounds such as chloride, nitrate, and sulfate and negatively charged metal complexes of iron, nickel, and zinc by ion exchange increased solvent degradation. The authors discuss that the formation of metal ion complexes might stabilize the redox behaviour of metal cations dissolved in the solvent and that removing these components leads to increased catalytic activity of degradation reactions.
- Treating the solvent with an active carbon filter had no clear effect on its degradation rate and performance, despite reducing its visible absorbance and the concentrations of iron, nickel, and chloride.

4.3 Campaigns at WtE plants

Three solvent-based CO₂ capture campaigns have been carried out on flue gas from WtE plants, namely at Amager Bakke in Denmark [4], Fortum Oslo Varme (now Hafslund Oslo Celsio)

Klemetsrud plant in Norway [6] and AVR Duiven in the Netherlands [5]. A brief summary of each of these campaigns is given in this section.

4.3.1 Amager Bakke

A four-month test campaign using 30 wt% MEA as the solvent was carried out at Amager Bakke in 2021. Table 4-3 shows the typical composition of the flue gas (half-hour average values) based on plant measurements. In addition to the air pollution control system at Amager Bakke, a filter to remove HCl was placed upstream of the CO₂ capture pilot, probably as a precautionary measure. The authors mention that a similar gas cleaning step would likely also be part of a full-scale installation, indicating that a scrubber could be used for this purpose. As discussed in Section 3.3, periods with higher dust concentrations and other contaminants (for example, CO and total organic carbon) can occur during startups, shutdowns and various operational disturbances. This was taken into account during the design of the capture plant; more details can be found in Neerup et al. (2023) [4].

Table 4-3: Typical flue gas composition at Amager Bakke (half-hour average values [4]).

Component	Unit	Value
H ₂ O	vol%	13.5
O ₂ (dry)	vol%	7.25
CO ₂ (dry)	vol%	12.3
CO	mg/Nm ³	3
TOC	mg/Nm ³	1
Dust	mg/Nm ³	1
HCl	mg/Nm ³	1
SO ₂	mg/Nm ³	1.5
HF	mg/Nm ³	0.1
NO	mg/Nm ³	20
NO ₂	mg/Nm ³	0.2
NH ₃	mg/Nm ³	1
Hg	mg/Nm ³	0.001
Dioxins and furans	ng/Nm ³	0.002

Fresh MEA was occasionally added during the test to keep the solvent concentration around the setpoint of 30 wt%. A carbon filter was also installed to clean the solvent, stabilising the iron concentration. The main solvent degradation products observed during the campaign were formate, acetate, sulfate and nitrate. This indicates that oxidative degradation and reactions with NO_x and SO_x are the main reasons for solvent losses. The formation of heat-stable salts (such as oxalate and formate) that accumulate in the solvent was found to be the main issue during the test. No problems caused by HCl or HF in the flue gas are discussed, indicating that the additional cleaning stage is sufficient to avoid such issues.

4.3.2 Fortum Oslo Varme

In 2019, Shell's proprietary solvent DC-103 was tested for over 5000 hours at Fortum Oslo Varme's (now Hafslund Oslo Celsio) Klemetsrud facility. The pilot plant receives a mix of flue gas from three lines at the WtE plant, and the yearly average composition is shown in Table 4-4. No additional gas cleaning was performed before the pilot plant, and no solvent make-up was added during the campaign. After around 5000 hours of operation, the concentration of degradation products was around 5 wt%, corresponding to approximately 10% degradation of the solvent inventory. The results do not clearly show whether the degradation is caused mainly by

oxidation or other mechanisms. Due to an incident at the plant, a period of higher dust concentrations was observed, which caused a significant increase in the amine emissions from the pilot plant. Based on the results from the campaign, the authors recommended that a thermal reclaiming unit for removing degradation products from the solvent should be installed for a full-scale installation. Towards the end of the test campaign, there seemed to be an increase in the solvent degradation rate. However, the test duration was not long enough to determine if the solvent had reached an exponential degradation regime.

Table 4-4: Flue gas composition at the Klemetsrud WtE plant (yearly average values) [6].

Component	Unit	Value
H ₂ O	vol%	13.9
O ₂ (dry)	vol%	7.3
CO ₂ (dry)	vol%	11.3
CO	mg/Nm ³	23.1
HCl	mg/Nm ³	0.8
SO ₂	mg/Nm ³	7.0
NO	mg/Nm ³	43.9
NO ₂	mg/Nm ³	1.2
NH ₃	mg/Nm ³	2.0
H ₂ S	mg/Nm ³	0.3

4.3.3 AVR Duiven

A commercial CO₂ capture plant using aqueous MEA as the solvent is in operation at AVR Duiven. Results from three separate campaigns from 2020 and 2021 have been presented and discussed in [5]. A summary is given below:

- Higher solvent degradation than the long-term MEA test at Niederaussem was observed.
- The authors list the following reasons for higher solvent losses:
 - The pilot plant at Niederaussem is better controlled, avoiding large fluctuations in the solvent concentration.
 - The flue gas oxygen concentration is higher at AVR Duiven, which will influence the degradation rate (as seen in Figure 4-4).
 - The bleed and feed strategy implemented for solvent management was unsuitable for keeping the iron concentration low. This was expected to contribute to accelerated solvent degradation.
- The analysis emphasises oxidative degradation products, indicating that this is the most important cause of solvent losses at AVR Duiven.

4.4 Comparison of emission levels from WtE plants and CO₂ capture plant requirements

The pilot plant campaigns summarised in this chapter show that it is possible to operate solvent-based CO₂ capture processes on a wide range of flue gas contaminant concentrations. Even after the long-term test of AMP/PZ at Niederaussem, lasting over 40 months, it was impossible to identify strict limits for contaminant concentrations in the flue gas. As pointed out by Buvik et al [3], there is likely a connection between the degree of flue gas treatment and the stability of the solvent. However, for flue gas contaminant concentrations in the range of the BAT-AELs for WtE plants, there are no clear, general indications that successful operation of a CO₂ capture plant

would not be possible, albeit with the risk of reduced capture efficiency and increased solvent consumption.

Due to the variations in emission characteristics between WtE plants and even individual lines within the same plant, additional flue gas treatment would need to be determined on a case-by-case basis. In some of the pilot campaigns, additional flue gas cleaning was performed prior to the CO₂ capture process to lower the concentrations of certain components beyond the BAT-AELs. The techno-economic implications of these modifications are interesting to study in more detail since they might be needed in some cases to make a WtE plant capture-ready. The following additional purification steps have been mentioned:

- 1) Dosing the direct contact cooler (DCC) with caustic soda for increased acid gas removal.
- 2) Filters for removal of HCl.

The experimental campaigns indicate that the oxygen concentration in the flue gas is a critical factor for solvent stability, which is expected since oxidative degradation is an important route for solvent losses in amine-based systems. Therefore, alternatives for reducing the oxygen concentration in the flue gas could be interesting to consider. This would likely involve adjusting the operation of the WtE plant rather than investing in downstream units to remove oxygen from the flue gas. The costs associated with additional gas cleaning stages or modified plant operation must be compared to the alternative costs of allowing higher solvent degradation rates and emissions from the capture plant.

5 TECHNO-ECONOMIC CASE STUDIES ON SENSITIVITY OF SOLVENT DEGRADATION TO FLUE GAS IMPURITIES

This section provides simple techno-economic calculation examples and a qualitative discussion of the possible measures identified throughout the previous sections associated with reducing impurities in the flue gas and its impact on solvent degradation.

5.1 NaOH-dosing of DCC for additional acid gas removal

In most cases, a direct contact cooler is used to saturate the flue gas with water and cool it to the required temperature for CO₂ absorption. The DCC can be further utilised for additional acid gas removal from the flue gas when necessary. This can be achieved by dosing the DCC with NaOH (caustic soda). This subsection estimates the increased operating costs associated with this additional cleaning step based on the SO₂ removal rate reported for the Niederaussem pilot plant. At this plant, the maximum SO₂ concentration at the DCC inlet was 160 mg/Nm³ and the outlet concentration was below 1 mg/Nm³. Therefore, this calculation example uses a concentration difference of 159 mg/Nm³. The following reactions take place between NaOH and SO₂³:

The ratio between the different reaction products depends on the pH and degree of oxidation. In this case, the extent of each reaction is assumed to be equal, meaning that the molar ratio between NaOH and SO₂ is 1.67 in the reactions. Using a dry flue gas flow rate of 70 000 Nm³/h, around the scale of the KVA Linth WtE plant in Switzerland, this corresponds to a NaOH consumption of 11.6 kg/h for the SO₂ concentration difference given above. Assuming continuous operation of the DCC, the yearly NaOH consumption becomes 101.6 metric tons. Based on an average of two different sources^{4,5}, adjusted to 2023 values using the industrial producer price index⁶, an NaOH price of 352.6 €/ton was found. This gives an additional cost of 35.8 k€/year related to the consumption of NaOH. Key numbers from the estimation are shown in Table 5-1. This estimate includes no costs associated with the post-processing of the aqueous reaction product leaving the DCC. This treatment stage typically involves neutralisation and precipitation of heavy metals.

³ Schnelle, Karl B. and Brown, Charles A. Air pollution control technology handbook. eng. Mechanical engineering handbook series. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2002. ISBN: 0-8493-9588-7

⁴ INTRATEC Caustic Soda Prices. <https://www.intratec.us/chemical-markets/caustic-soda-price> (accessed 2024-04-08)

⁵ Business Analytiq Caustic Soda price index: <https://businessanalytiq.com/procurementanalytics/index/caustic-soda-price-index/> (accessed 2024-04-08).

⁶ Eurostat industrial producer price index overview (accessed 2024-04-08).

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Industrial_producer_price_index_overview

Table 5-1: Key numbers from estimate of increased operating cost related to NaOH-dosing of DCC.

	Unit	Value
SO ₂ inlet concentration to DCC	mg/Nm ³ (dry)	160
SO ₂ outlet concentration after DCC	mg/Nm ³ (dry)	1
SO ₂ concentration difference	mg/Nm ³ (dry)	159
Total flue gas flow rate	Nm ³ /h (dry)	70 000
Municipal solid waste mass flow	tons/y	120 000
Molar ratio between NaOH and SO ₂	-	1.67
SO ₂ removal rate	kg/h	11.1
NaOH hourly consumption	kg/h	11.6
NaOH yearly consumption	tons/y	101.6
NaOH specific cost	€/ton	352.6
Operating costs related to NaOH	k€/y	35.8

Although the calculation example above focuses on SO₂, NaOH-dosing of the DCC will also contribute to removing other acid gases, such as HCl and HF. Due to the high water solubility of HCl and HF, a regular DCC operated with only water might be sufficient to remove these species from the flue gas before the CO₂ capture plant. The only pilot plant (on our list) that needed additional HCl removal before the absorber was Amager Bakke, which is one of the few facilities without a DCC. As pointed out by Neerup et al. [4], a scrubber would likely be used instead of an impregnated activated carbon filter for acid gas removal for a full-scale installation.

As mentioned in the BREF WI, an advantage of using a caustic soda solution is that the reaction products are water-soluble, reducing the risk of deposition in the DCC. CaCO₃ deposits may form that need to be removed periodically by acidification depending on the water hardness. From the chemical reactions between SO₂ and NaOH listed above, it is seen that O₂ is consumed in the formation of Na₂SO₄. Reducing the flue gas oxygen content would be beneficial regarding solvent degradation, but the change in O₂ concentration from this reaction is not expected to be significant.

5.2 Effect of degradation rate on operating cost

In the CO₂ capture pilot studies summarised in this report, solvent consumption rates due to degradation in the 0.5 to 2 kg/t CO₂ range have been reported. In other campaigns, solvent losses as high as 3.5 kg/t CO₂ have been observed [5]. To understand the costs associated with such solvent losses, a calculation example for AMP/PZ is given in this section. In [11], an AMP price of 8.0 €/kg and PZ price of 6.0 €/kg is reported. In the ACCSESS project reference solvent mixture, the mass-based ratio between AMP and PZ in the solvent is around 2. Considering this composition, the solvent mixture's cost becomes 7.35 €/kg.

Considering a flue gas flow of 70 000 Nm³/h with an average dry CO₂ concentration of 12.8 vol%, the total mass flow of CO₂ in the flue gas is 17.6 ton/h. Assuming continuous operation and an average capture rate of 90%, the yearly amount of captured CO₂ is 138.7 kton/y. For a plant of this size, the relationship between degradation rates from 0.25-3.5 kg/t CO₂ and the solvent replacement cost is shown in Figure 5-1. Solvent replacement costs between 255 and 3567 k€/year are estimated.

Figure 5-1: Solvent replacement cost vs. solvent consumption due to degradation for AMP/PZ for the reference plant with a captured CO₂ amount of 138.7 kt/year.

The key numbers used in the calculation are summarised in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Key numbers behind estimation of solvent replacement costs.

	Unit	Value
Total flue gas flow rate	Nm ³ /h (dry)	70 000
Municipal solid waste mass flow	tons/y	120 000
Average CO ₂ concentration	vol% (dry)	12.8
CO ₂ mass flow in the flue gas	ton/h	17.6
CO ₂ capture rate	%	90
Yearly amount of captured CO ₂	kton/y	138.7
Cost of AMP/PZ solvent	€/kg	7.35
Range of solvent degradation rates	kg/t CO ₂	0.25 – 3.5

5.3 Management of flue gas oxygen concentration

Oxidative degradation is a dominant mechanism in the absorption process [Buvik et al. 2021, Vega et al. 2014]. This is also a clear indication from Figure 4-4, showing the relationship between flue gas oxygen concentration and solvent degradation. The number of data points is limited, and care should be taken when using these figures to conclude on solvent degradation and replacement, especially since several factors can contribute to the reduced degradation rate. However, if the trend as shown in Figure 4-4 is generally valid also for WtE plants, a rough estimation can be done:

- For the reference O₂ concentration of 11 vol-% dry, the solvent degradation rate can be roughly estimated at 1.7 kg/t CO₂ from Figure 4-4. For the model plant described above, with a captured amount of CO₂ of 138.7 kton/year, the solvent replacement cost will be about 1.7 million € per year.
- If the O₂ concentration is reduced to 7 vol-% dry, the degradation rate could be reduced to about 1.4 kg/t CO₂, with a solvent replacement cost of about 1.4 million € per year.

- If the O₂ concentration could be reduced further down, the solvent degradation rate drops steeply, down to about 0.5 kg/t CO₂ at an O₂ concentration of 5 vol- % dry. The solvent costs would be about 0.5 million € per year, and the savings on solvent replacement, compared with reference O₂ concentration, amounts to about 1.2 million € per year.

Reduction of excess air and/or recirculating flue gas will reduce the flue gas O₂ concentration. Such measures have been explored for many years in the WtE sector due to the possible positive effects on NO_x generation, reduced flue gas volumes, reduced thermal losses and increased plant efficiency. When adding CO₂ capture to a WtE plant, there will be an added motivation factor for implementing solutions that can help keep flue gas O₂ concentration as low as possible due to the positive effect on solvent degradation rate. However, the example above indicates that a low O₂ concentration should be reached to see possible considerable savings on solvent replacement cost. Such low excess air and too much flue gas recirculation can increase corrosion risks. They would lead to poor waste incineration and gas burnout, causing products from incomplete combustion to leave with the flue gas. Another factor is the heterogeneous nature of MSW, causing possible significant variations over the incineration grate area, and the need for efficient mixing by the secondary air injections to ensure complete burnout and homogenisation of gas composition and temperature through the empty passes and into the boiler. In such conditions, operating close to the air excess limit is difficult, with limited margins before, e.g., CO levels will rise sharply.

A full-scale study has been performed on the reduction of O₂ concentration in a grate-fired incinerator using a mixture of municipal and industrial waste [12]. The plant also has a possibility of flue gas recirculation. They state that traditional WtE plants operate with oxygen concentrations above 5 vol-% (wet) measured at the boiler exit. This is approximately equivalent to above 6 vol-% dry basis, at the low end of the WtE lines analysed in chapter 3.3.7. At this oxygen concentration, 5 vol-% (wet), they measured uncontrolled NO_x concentrations of 225 mg/Nm³ when corrected to 11 vol-% O₂ dry. Uncontrolled means this is the NO_x concentration from the combustion process before any secondary NO_x reduction measures such as SNCR or SCR have been used. Reducing the O₂ concentration to 3 vol-% wet, the NO_x concentration was reduced to about 150 mg/Nm³ at 11 vol-% O₂ dry.

Further reduction could be obtained by reducing the O₂ concentration even more, down towards 2 vol-% wet. However, when NO_x concentrations approached 100 mg/Nm³ and below, the CO concentrations increased sharply. It was concluded that this specific plant could operate on an optimum NO_x concentration between 100 and 150 mg/Nm³, without an increase in CO, with an O₂ setpoint between 2 and 3 vol-% (wet), corresponding to air excess values below 20%.

Strobel et al. [12] also showed the importance of an optimised and automated combustion control system for running stable at the low end of NO_x and O₂ concentrations shown above. Improvements to the combustion control system, with additional sensors and measuring devices, can be of higher importance when adding CCS to a WtE plant. The combined result of several positive effects and their possible economic upside might justify such investments.

6 CAPTURE-READY WTE PLANTS

Waste-to-energy plants effectively manage municipal solid waste, reducing the need for landfilling and associated environmental impacts. Waste-to-energy plants generate renewable electricity and heat by converting non-recyclable waste into energy, reducing reliance on fossil fuels. Integrating carbon capture enhances the sustainability of this waste management approach, allowing the reduction of fossil emissions and unlocking the potential for negative emissions due to a significant biogenic share of the waste.

While the earlier sections focused on existing plants and retrofitting them with CO₂ capture, future WtE plants are expected to be built with CO₂ capture in mind—that is, they will be capture-ready. Incorporating carbon capture readiness into new WtE plants or retrofitting existing ones prepares these facilities for potential future regulations and policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, ensuring their long-term viability.

This section provides critical recommendations for CO₂ capture-ready WtE plants based on the earlier sections.

6.1 Feasibility studies

Comprehensive feasibility studies to assess the technical, economic, and environmental viability of implementing CO₂ capture technologies in the specific waste-to-energy facility are essential in designing a capture-ready WtE plant. This allows evaluating potential capture technologies, considering cost, efficiency, maturity, and scalability. Important aspects of performing these feasibility studies are:

Flue gas composition fluctuations and APC/FGT

The heterogeneity of MSW is reflected in the MSW flue gas: its composition varies over time (different scales) and contains many contaminants at various levels. The fluctuations experienced in operation can be large (up to several orders of magnitude) and last several minutes or even hours. This variability in flue gas composition encompasses CO₂ concentration, impurities (like sulphur oxides, nitrogen oxides, and particulate matter), and moisture content. This must be considered when integrating CO₂ capture to limit operational challenges (e.g., corrosion) and CO₂ capture-related issues (e.g., solvent degradation).

To mitigate these challenges, WtE plants with CO₂ capture systems require robust flue gas pretreatment systems to remove impurities and maintain a consistent gas composition. Adapting/improving the existing FGT system and eventually adding new cleaning steps are two important measures to be considered in CCS-ready WtE plants. (But this requires clear requirements from the CCS process). Some clear recommendations related to APC systems are:

- ESP for dust removal and add additional bag filters if required
- SCR for NO_x removal to achieve low NO_x levels in flue gas
- Wet scrubbers for acid gas removal
- Optional NaOH dosing in DCC as an additional polishing/cleaning step based on plant performance

Advanced monitoring and control systems are also essential to detect and respond to real-time fluctuations, ensuring efficient and reliable CO₂ capture operations. Furthermore, properly

characterising the waste feedstock and its variability is crucial for designing and optimising the capture system to handle the expected range of flue gas compositions.

Integration with energy recovery - Maintaining stable operation and energy delivery

Maintaining stable operation and energy delivery is critical for WtE plants as they produce heat for district heating and/or electricity. Solvent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture mainly uses thermal energy for solvent regeneration. The thermal energy for solvent regeneration can be supplied by extracting steam from the steam cycle of the WtE plant. Figure 6-1 shows the energy flows in a WtE plant integrated with solvent-based post-combustion capture.

Figure 6-1: Energy flows in WtE plant integrated with solvent-based post-combustion CO₂ capture

Steam extraction from the steam cycle in the WtE plant will affect the net power generation and heat available for the district heating supply. Appropriate design and integration with an energy recovery system are critical to maintaining suitable production levels of heat and/or electricity. This will include appropriate design (or modification in the case of retrofit) of the steam turbines to minimise the impact of the CO₂ capture plant. Heat pumps are an essential technology for plants that supply district heating to maintain production levels. The relative importance of exporting heat compared to electricity, the steam parameters in the facility, and the CO₂ capture technology (in terms of the quality and quantity of heat required for solvent regeneration) will affect the type of integration.

CO₂ conditioning and transport logistics

The CO₂ from solvent-based capture technologies is pure. Based on the most suitable transportation option for the facility, this CO₂ stream must be compressed to a dense phase (liquid or supercritical).

Once the CO₂ is conditioned, transportation to suitable storage sites or utilisation facilities becomes a critical logistical challenge. The transport logistics for capture-ready WtE plants may involve a combination of the following modes:

- Pipeline Transport: For large-scale CO₂ volumes and relatively short distances, pipelines can be an economical and efficient mode of transportation. However, this is most relevant

when the plant is close to an existing network. Otherwise, the initial capital investment for pipeline infrastructure can be substantial.

- **Truck Transport:** For smaller CO₂ volumes or when the plant is located far from storage sites or pipeline networks, truck transportation using specialised tankers or cryogenic containers may be more feasible. This mode offers flexibility but can be more expensive for larger volumes and longer distances.
- **Barge/Ship Transport:** Barge or ship transportation of liquefied CO₂ can be a viable option for plants near navigable rivers or coastal areas.

The choice of transportation mode depends on factors such as the plant's location, the volume of CO₂ captured, the distance to storage sites, and the availability of existing infrastructure. Careful planning and coordination with relevant stakeholders, including pipeline operators, shipping companies, and storage site operators, are essential to ensure a seamless and cost-effective CO₂ transport logistics system.

6.2 Integration Planning and Logistics

The installation of a carbon capture plant requires a significant area. For example, IEAGHG indicates that the space for constructing a carbon capture plant to retrofit a 20MWe net power WtE is approximately 25m x 40m.

While new plants can easily integrate this demand at the planning stage and take the necessary measures early on, existing plants might need help, especially in densely built areas. Their neighbours might not be willing to relocate, and/or the costs to buy space might be high, impacting CCS CAPEX. However, the capture section of CCS is only a part of the overall logistics required. Temporary storage and conditioning and transport to a central storage/conditioning site (via pipelines, trucks, boats and combinations thereof) can become logistics nightmares requiring energy and space. Hence, each WtE plant will have to design its tailored solutions, balancing costs and benefits, limitations, and opportunities as best as possible.

6.3 Flexible design and operation

The WtE and CO₂ capture plant should be designed to be flexible, accommodating advancements in CO₂ capture technologies as they evolve. For example, solvents can be replaced as new solvents come to market, affecting the energy integration with the plant. Additionally, flexibility in capture based on seasonal operation could be an important factor for some WtE plants. WtE plants producing only or primarily heat for district heating will have “excess heat” available in summer.

Integrating CO₂ capture systems is essential to ensuring the plant's overall efficiency and waste treatment capabilities are not compromised. In other words, a significant aspect of capture readiness is that it should not disturb WtE's existing key missions—reducing unrecyclable waste volume and mass, destroying contaminants, and concentrating pollutants for final safe disposal.

6.4 Regulatory compliance

The WtE sector is heavily regulated and monitored, and rightly so, with BREF BAT WI being a central document. WtE is also at the nexus of many other interests and its own sets of regulations/goals/visions, from (renewable) energy production to material recovery targets but also EC taxonomy and ETS, to name a few. CO₂ capture readiness will have to navigate in this complex universe but will also require adjustments regarding existing practices (e.g. permitting). This must be discussed as early as possible to avoid losing months or years to such questions.

Proactively anticipating compliance challenges (especially via organisations/associations) is the better approach.

6.5 Life cycle assessment (LCA)

It is essential to conduct a comprehensive lifecycle assessment to evaluate the environmental impact of CO₂ capture technologies, considering aspects like energy consumption, materials, and waste generation. LCA will provide a complete overview of CCS in WtE and help pinpoint where the main efforts must be put to reduce negative impacts and quantify the positive effects of CCS WtE. However, indicators and functional units must be carefully considered and discussed when evaluating the combined impacts of CCS and WtE. The LCA will also be critical when considering the negative emissions potential of the WtE plant with CO₂ capture.

6.6 Collaboration and research

Fundamental research, applied research and development, and innovation are essential to capture-ready WtE plants. As in most sectors, incremental improvements and breakthroughs will make CCS more accessible to WtE actors. Solving/curbing the many technical challenges, from corrosion to solvent degradation, robustness/flexibility and energy consumption, will ensure smooth CCS readiness. Furthermore, expanding the technical choices and alternatives will press down costs and promote emulation, especially when a one-size-fits-all approach is wrong.

6.7 Operator training

CO₂ capture and WtE cannot be seen as two separate islands that are only connected by a few pipes exchanging flue gas and heat. CCS-ready WtE plants will require specifically trained operators and maintenance personnel who can handle this new breed of plants and understand them as a whole. Capture-ready WtE plants should thus invest in training programs for plant operators to ensure they are well-versed in the operation and maintenance of CO₂ capture systems. Establishing clear protocols for monitoring and reporting captured CO₂ data will also be necessary.

6.8 Financial incentives and novel business models

CCS has significant CAPEX and OPEX, and there will likely be no one-size-fits business model to finance and operate it. First-of-its-kind plants might have access to significant subsidies, but subsequent plants will need to implement more economically viable solutions. Given the vast variety of situations in Europe, various alternatives and combinations will probably appear, e.g. increased gate fees; certification of some kind (example: Plastic Elimination Certificates (PECs)); reverse auction; CAPEX & OPEX subsidies/incentives/tax breaks; negative emission credits.

CO₂ utilisation can provide a potential revenue stream for a small subset of waste-to-energy (WtE) plants by selling captured CO₂ for applications like greenhouse enrichment and algae cultivation. However, the demand and market for utilising CO₂ emissions are currently limited, making it viable only for WtE plants near facilities that can use the captured CO₂, such as greenhouses or algae farms.

The key potential revenue streams from CO₂ utilisation for WtE plants are:

- The sale of CO₂ to nearby greenhouses is used to enhance crop yields, which can increase yields by up to 25-30%. The Netherlands is a leader in this application, consuming around 500 ktCO₂ annually from external sources for its greenhouses.

- Sale of CO₂ for algae cultivation to produce biofuels and other products, although this application is still in the early development stages.
- Potential sale of CO₂ for other chemical processes like fertiliser and methanol production, where additional CO₂ can enhance yields.

The feasibility of these revenue streams depends on factors like proximity to demand sources (ideally within 5-10 km), availability of CO₂ transportation infrastructure, and the costs of capturing, purifying, and transporting the CO₂ compared to potential revenues. Overall, CO₂ utilisation opportunities are limited to a small number of strategically located WtE plants near suitable off-takers.

6.9 Community engagement and public perception

A CCS-ready WtE sector means much more than solving technical problems in an economic and environmentally sound manner. It also means addressing public questions and concerns and engaging with the whole society to build trust and even support. This may involve communication campaigns, community outreach (including children and educational institutions), and transparency in decision-making processes. Many decisions involve all of us as a society and have far-reaching implications that should be understood and accepted by as many as possible.

7 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This deliverable provides an overview of the challenges of integrating solvent-based CO₂ capture in a WtE plant, focusing on the interface between the air pollution control/flue gas treatment section and the CO₂ capture unit. In an IEAGHG technical report on CCS from WtE, the following concentration limits were recommended to keep the solvent degradation at acceptable levels [2]:

- Maximum SO₂ concentration: 10 ppm
- Maximum NO_x (as NO₂) concentration: 20 ppm
- Maximum total dust concentration: 10 ppm
- Maximum HCl concentration: 10 ppm

The current BAT-AELs on waste incineration, as well as operational data from WtE plants, show that continuously keeping the concentration of SO₂, NO_x and dust below the levels recommended by IEAGHG is unlikely. However, pilot campaign experience shows that solvent-based CO₂ capture plants can successfully operate on a range of flue gas contaminant concentrations. The impact on CO₂ capture plant efficiency and solvent degradation (and thus operating costs) needs to be clarified in such situations. Therefore, for flue gas contaminant concentrations in the range of the BAT-AELs for WtE plants, there are no clear, general indications that successful operation of a CO₂ capture plant would not be possible, albeit with challenges and limitations (e.g. risk of corrosion, increased OPEX).

Additional acid gas removal steps have been implemented in a few demonstration plants before CO₂ capture pilot plants, going beyond the BAT-AELs. In this work, we quantified, in a simple manner, the tradeoff between the cost of solvent replacement due to degradation and additional cleaning of the flue gas using NaOH-dosing in the direct contact cooler (DCC). The cost of utilising the DCC of the carbon capture unit for additional acid gas removal by NaOH-dosing is significantly lower than the cost associated with solvent replacement due to degradation.

The relationship between oxygen concentration and solvent degradation provides an additional motivation for implementing solutions that can help keep flue gas O₂ concentration as low as possible at WtE plants. However, this could be challenging to achieve in practice and might require optimised combustion control systems with increased monitoring.

Recommendations for capture-ready WtE plant implementation have been provided as part of this work. It is essential to remember that there is no one-size-fits-all solution; each line is unique and requires a case-to-case study, mainly due to heterogeneous and varying MSW composition and a tailored FGT. Additionally, improvement of combustion control system incl. additional and/or new sensors and measuring devices for optimal "dual/integrated" operation of WtE and CCS (that should not be seen as separate islands) will probably be an essential measure to ensure smooth implementation of capture-ready WtE plants.

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APPENDIX

A: BAT-associated emission levels in ppm

Emission values will often be needed as volumetric ppm values. They can be found from the mg/Nm³ values using the following conversion:

$$[ppm] = \left[\frac{mg}{Nm^3} \right] \cdot \frac{V_{mole}}{M_i},$$

where V_{mole} is the volume of one kmol of flue gas at normal condition (22.4 Nm³/kmol) and M_i is the molecular weight of the flue gas component. NO_x is expressed as NO₂ and should use the molecular weight of NO₂. TVOC is expressed as C and its molecular weight should be used. The BAT-AEL's recalculated to ppm is shown in Table A-1 for those components where a value for the molecular weight is clearly defined. For flue gas compounds where several different components are summed, there is no clear molecular weight to use, and they are therefore not included. For dust it is even more difficult, having no relevant molecular weight to use. A ppm value for dust should probably be based on counting dust particles in relevant size ranges.

Table A-1: BAT-AEL's shown in mg/Nm³ and ppm. All values at normal condition (temperature 0 °C and 1 atmosphere pressure), and a reference oxygen concentration of 11 vol-% dry.

Flue gas compounds	Molecular weight	Emission unit 1				Emission unit 2					
		New plant		Existing plant		New plant		Existing plant			
SO ₂	64.1	mg/Nm ³	5	30	5	40	ppm	1.7	10.5	1.7	14.0
HCl	36.5	mg/Nm ³	2	6	2	8	ppm	1.2	3.7	1.2	4.9
HF	20.0	mg/Nm ³	1	1	1	1	ppm	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1
NO _x (as NO ₂)	46.0	mg/Nm ³	50	120	50	150	ppm	24.4	58.5	24.4	73.1
CO	28.0	mg/Nm ³	10	50	10	50	ppm	8.0	40.0	8.0	40.0
NH ₃	17.0	mg/Nm ³	2	10	2	10	ppm	2.6	13.2	2.6	13.2
Dust	---	mg/Nm ³	2	5	2	5	---				
Cd+Tl	---	mg/Nm ³	0.005	0.02	0.005	0.02	---				
Sb+As+Pb+Cr+Co+Cu+Mn+Ni+V	---	mg/Nm ³	0.01	0.3	0.01	0.3	---				
TVOC (as C)	12.0	mg/Nm ³	3	10	3	10	ppm	5.6	18.7	5.6	18.7
PCDD/F	---	ng I-TEQ/Nm ³	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.06	---				
PCDD/F + dioxin-like PCBs	---	ng WHO-TEQ/Nm ³	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.08	---				
Hg	200.6	µg/Nm ³	5	20	5	20	ppm	0.0006	0.0022	0.0006	0.0022

B: APC technologies employed on reference lines in BREF WI

In the BREF WI, the APC technologies employed on reference lines in Europe were summarized as part of the 2016 data collection. The collection comprises between 322 and 346 lines. The APC technologies were grouped in acid gas reduction, dust reduction, and NO_x reduction technologies. Within each group they were further divided between the common techniques. A summary is shown in Figure B-1.

Acid gas removal is mainly done using dry sorbent injection (DSI), wet scrubber (WS), and DSI+WS. Together they account for 80 % of the lines. For dust removal, 54 % of the lines utilize only bag filters. Electrostatic precipitator (ESP) is used in the remaining 46 %, either alone or together with a bag filter. The NO_x reduction is mainly carried out using selective non-catalytic reduction (SNCR), about 52 %, and about 41 % of the reference lines in the data set are using selective catalytic reduction (SCR).

Figure B-1: Overview of APC technologies utilized on more than 300 reference lines in Europe from the 2016 data collection. DSI: Dry sorbent injection; SWS: Semi-wet scrubber; WS: Wet scrubber; ESP: Electrostatic precipitator; BF: Bag filter; SNCR: Selective non-catalytic reduction; SCR: Selective catalytic reduction.

C: Emission levels for reference lines in BREF WI

The 2016 data collection from the BREF WI includes emission data for 355 emissions monitoring points from WtE reference lines and plants used in the work with the BREF WI. Half-hourly average concentrations for year 2014 were collected for each of the continuously measured emission components. Figure C-1 to Figure C-9 below show values for the nine flue gas components SO₂, HCl, HF, NO_x, NH₃, CO, dust, TVOC, and Hg. The x-axis shows intervals of emission concentrations, and for each interval, the columns show how large percentage of the WtE reference lines that have emission values within that interval. The emission values for each line are averaged in three different ways: Yearly, Daily Base, and Daily Fine. The “base” and “fine” values are obtained using different filtering procedure. The “base” data excludes some measurements obtained when the plant is not in typical operation mode. The “fine” data excludes even more values related to upsets and other than normal conditions (see BREF WI for details).

In the bottom of the figures are also included pie charts showing the distribution of the emission reduction technologies that are used within each emission interval. For CO and TVOC, the bottom pie charts instead give a distribution of size divided in Small, Medium, and Large. This classification is done since CO and TVOC are important measures for the combustion efficiency and the scale has an impact. For MSW, the classification is done using the ranges:

- Small: less than 100 000 tonnes/year
- Medium: between 100 000 and 250 000 tonnes/year
- Large: more than 250 000 tonnes/year.

The red vertical lines included in each figure gives the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants. This provides an easy way to consider the situation (in 2014) in relation to new BAT-AEL’s, which all the plants must conform to from December 2023.

Figure C-1: Continuously monitored SO₂ emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-2: Continuously monitored HCl emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-3: Continuously monitored HF emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red line shows the BAT-AEL for existing plants (no interval, common lower and upper bound).

Figure C-4: Continuously monitored NO_x emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-5: Continuously monitored NH₃ emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-6: Continuously monitored CO emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-7: Continuously monitored dust emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-8: Continuously monitored TVOC emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

Figure C-9: Continuously monitored mercury (Hg) emissions to air from reference lines incinerating predominantly MSW (from BREF WI). The red lines show the lower and upper bound of the BAT-AEL for existing plants.

D: Emission levels and variations for ACCESS WtE lines

The results for each species are presented in the sub-sections below. The analysis covers periods of 4-12 months of operation and is meant to be representative of the plants' typical behaviour. Each sub-section below shows one figure per species with statistical parameters to describe normalised emissions for several WtE lines during normal, relatively stable operation. Numerals in the x-axis represent different lines and are grouped by the main features of the implemented air pollution control (APC) system on each line. Please note that the same number can refer to a different line in different figures (as the number of lines in each figure varies depending on data availability).

The statistical parameters included in Figures D1 to D6 are:

- The average value for the whole period (blue bar) +/- standard deviation (black vertical lines).
- The maximum value (orange circle) observed in the period studied (4-12 months). The value is divided by 10 to fit in the same scale.
- The percentage of measured points (% values given at the top of the figure) above the lower BAT-AEL bound (different depending on the species).

Additionally, WtE is subject to unstable, fluctuating conditions and periods with high emissions. These can significantly impact any downstream process, including carbon capture. Referring to these unstable conditions as "incidents," a quantitative/qualitative analysis is included to sum up their main characteristics and dynamics for several WtE lines.

One table (Tables D1 to D6) is included per species with information about:

- The peak value observed.
- How fast (in minutes/hours) does the increase (to the peak/high plateau) happens and how long does the decrease (from the peak/plateau) require.
- The typical duration of such an incident.
- How often does such an incident happen in a given WtE line.

NO_x emissions

Figure D-1 shows the statistical parameters during normal, relatively stable operation for 10 WtE lines. SCR is needed to achieve the low-end BAT-AEL values and below. It is also clear that these ten lines perform better than most lines in the BREF WI study.

Error! Reference source not found. shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from these ten lines. Peak values of slightly above 400 mg/Nm³ (~ 200 ppm) are encountered weekly or bi-weekly, lasting up to 3 – 5 hours. SNCR or SCR do not result in very different NO_x emissions during incidents, even though they show significant differences during normal operation.

Figure D-1: NOx emissions for 10 WtE lines (8/9/10 is one line divided into three 4-month periods). NOx BAT-AELs (daily average) for existing plant 50-150/180 (SCR/SNCR) and new plant 50-120.

Table D-1: Overview of some NOx incidents found in the data from the ten lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration & frequency	Comments
SCR dry	350-400	50 min & several hours	Over 5 hours & fortnight	Low CO ₂
SCR wet scr	224	>>>	1 hour (1 p) & monthly	-
SCR wet scr	No values above 100	-	-	Excluding start-up. More stable than L1.
SNCR wet	350	5 & 3 min	10 min & weekly+	Normal flow.
Id.	350-450	10 & 10 min	2.5-3 hours & weekly+	Low flow.
Id.	400-420	5 & 10 min	15 min & more than weekly (above 200)	Flow/combustion disturbances
Id.	300-350	10-12 & 10 min	1 hour & weekly+ (above 200)	Normal flow.
SNCR wet	300	15 & 10 min	30 min & weekly (above 100)	-
SCR dry	141	1 & 1 h (1 point)	1-2h & monthly+ (above 50)	"Overshoot" for 2-3h after peak (very low NOx).
SCR dry	191	1 & 1 h	2h & fortnight (above 50)	Often associated with low flow.
SCR wet scr	200-250	1-1.5 & 1-1.5 h	2h & monthly	-
SNCR dry	200	10-20 min	10-20 min, weekly	-

SO₂ emissions

Figure D-2 shows the statistical parameters for SO₂ emissions during normal, relatively stable operation for nine WtE lines. Most of the lines are below the lower BAT-AEL limit and well below the upper limit values. Maximum values are 100 mg/Nm³ and above 400 mg/Nm³, i.e. more than ten times the upper BAT-AEL limit.

Table D-2 shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from these nine lines.

Figure D-2: SO₂ emissions for 9 WtE lines (8/9/10 is one line divided into three 4-month periods). SO₂ BAT-AELs (daily average) for existing plant 5-40 and new plant 5-30.

Table D-2: Overview of some SO₂ incidents found in the data from the nine lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration frequency	& Comments
SCR dry	200-250	45min & 30 min	More than 1 hour & fortnight	Low CO ₂ .
SCR dry	400 (or 200-250)	Scattered for 2 hours	2 hours & fortnight	Low CO ₂ .
SCR wet scr	49	>>>	1 hour (1p) & seldom	-
SCR wet scr	Only 5 peaks above 40	...and all below 70, single points (1 hour)	-	Excluding start-up. More stable than L1.
SNCR wet	200	2 & 2 min	45 min & fortnight	Normal flow.
Id.	28	4-5 & 2-3 min	6 min & less than fortnight	Flow/combustion disturbances
Id.	40, 34 & 28	1 min	1 min & monthly (above 40)	Marked orange in Excel, why?
SCR dry	45	1 & 1h (1 point)	1-2h & weekly (above 5)	High HCl at the same time (13). Normal flow.
SCR dry	110	1 & 2h	7h & monthly (above 5)	Often associated with low flow.
SCR wet scr	-	-	-	1 point above 40, very low else.
SNCR dry	80-90	30 & 30 min	1h, several times a week	-

CO emissions

Figure D-3 shows the statistical parameters for CO emissions during normal, relatively stable operation for seven different WtE lines.

Table D-3 shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from these seven lines.

Figure D-3: CO emissions for 7 WtE lines. CO BAT-AELs (daily average) for existing and new plants 10-50.

Table D-3: Overview of some CO incidents found in the data from the seven lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration & frequency	Comments
SCR wet scr	16	1 point (1h) above 4	1h (1 point) & monthly (above 10)	-
SNCR wet	365	5 & 5 min	10 min & weekly+	Many points above low range
SCR wet scr	55	1 point	1 point & seldom (2 points > 35)	Many points above low range
SCR dry	-	-	-	CO <u>always</u> above 10
SCR dry	Up to 100-150	1h	Daily	(Almost) always above 10
SCR wet scr	Above 50	Short (10 min)	Short (10 min), several times a week	-
SNCR dry	Above 50-100	Short	Short, weekly+	Large standard deviation

Dust emissions

Figure D-4 shows the statistical parameters for dust emissions during normal, relatively stable operation for seven different WtE lines.

Table D-4 shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from these seven lines.

Figure D-4: Dust emissions for 7 WtE lines. Dust BAT-AELs (daily average) for existing and new plants 2-5.

Table D-4: Overview of some dust incidents found in the data from the seven lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration & frequency	Comments
SCR wet scr	2-3	5 points (above 2) in 1 day	1-2h & seldom (10 points in 1 year)	No problem if the filter is not damaged
SNCR wet	10-11 (4-6 mainly)	20 & 40 min	Ca. 4 hours & monthly (above 10)	-
SCR wet scr	-	-	-	All points below 2 except a couple near restart
SCR dry	50	1 & 2 h	2h & every other month (above 10)	Often associated with reduced flow
SCR dry	2 points above 2	-	-	Lower than L1
SCR wet scr	6-8	1 point	1 point every 4 hour	Connected to filter cleaning/flushing
SNCR dry	3-4	1 point	1 point every day	Connected to filter cleaning/flushing

HCl emissions

Figure D-5 shows the statistical parameters for HCl emissions during normal, relatively stable operation for six different WtE lines.

Table D-5 shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from the six lines.

Figure D-5: HCl emissions for 6 WtE lines. BAT-AELs for HCl (daily average) are for existing plants 2-8 and new plants 2-6. (Note: line 6 in the figure is SNCR dry).

Table D-5: Overview of some HCl incidents found in the data from the ACCESS lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration & frequency	Comments
SCR wet scr	3.5	3 h & 10 h	17-18 h & weekly (above 2)	-
SCR wet scr	-	-	-	Low and stable
SCR dry	48	5 & 8h	12h (4 above 8) & monthly (above 8)	Often associated with reduced flow
SCR dry	47	1h & 2h	7h & monthly (above 8)	Lower than L1. Often associated with low flow.
SCR wet scr	-	-	-	No point above 6
SNCR dry	8-10+	20/40 min up & down	1h, weekly	-

NH₃ emissions

Figure D-6 shows the statistical parameters for NH₃ emissions during regular, relatively stable operation for 6 WtE lines.

Table D-6 shows an overview of some relevant incidents found in the data from the ACCESS lines.

Figure D-6: NH₃ emissions for 6 WtE lines. BAT-AELs (daily average) 2-10.

Table D-6: Overview of some NH₃ incidents found in the data from the six lines.

Lines	Peak value	Dynamic (up & down)	Duration & frequency	Comments
SCR wet scr	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	Very stable (max is 1 point, other points below 2)
SCR wet scr	2 points on first day	2 points, 2 hours	2 hours & seldom	Many 0s, correct?
SCR dry	Only 6 episodes above 2	-	-	Often around flow disturbance or after stop
SCR dry	Few episodes above 2...	-	-	...only with disturbed flow/stop/start
SCR wet scr	20	3 & 3 h	6h, daily	More large variations
SNCR dry	20-30	1 & 1 h	2-4h, weekly	Some "bad", longer periods